

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SPECIFICS OF USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS AS A METHOD FOR DEVELOPING FOREIGN LANGUAGE SPEECH MONOLOGUE SKILLS

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Abstract

The development of monologue speech skills should always be based on the development of the ability to build a coherent statement that clearly states a position or idea. Often it is the difficulties in constructing a logical statement that are the main problem for students in preparing a monologue. For the proper development of monologue skills, an effective technique is to use authentic texts as a basis and example. Fabulous texts can serve as both an example for a full-fledged monologue statement and a thematic example, the retelling of which will serve as an excellent training for monologue skills. The use of authentic story texts in foreign language classes is an effective method for developing students' monologue skills.

Keywords: monologue skills, authentic texts, fabulous text, plot text, home reading, retelling.

Introduction

Reading authentic literature is one of the ways to get acquainted with the peculiarities of constructing texts and presenting a certain idea in the text. In the process of learning a foreign language, reading authentic texts allows students to immerse themselves in the natural linguistic environment, experience the cultural and linguistic mentality, study interesting phraseology, and learn many new words and expressions. Reading fable texts both in class and in the process of reading at home is one of the aspects of language training of students, provides a more robust formation of various skills of communicative competence (linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive, sociocultural), and therefore is an important aspect of the process of teaching foreign languages.

Reading is one of the core competencies that students must master as part of the school curriculum.

Home reading is one of the forms of independent work for students to study a foreign language. Home reading is mandatory for all students, additional to the textbook, constant reading in order to extract meaningful information [1, p. 253]. In the context of developing monologue skills, reading authentic fable texts is a type of exercise that allows you to develop several skills in parallel. At the same time, for the effective development of all skills, the teacher checks the fact that students are completing home reading. For these purposes, reflection exercises and consolidation of the material read by students at home should be performed in lessons. In the context of reflection, a teacher can effectively use different types of tasks (retelling, answering questions, writing a short story by students) to develop monologue speech skills based on a plot text.

Materials and type of research

Objectives of the study: first, to determine the relationship between the development of reading skills

and the development of monologue speech; second, determine the specifics of using plot texts to develop listening skills; third, develop a set of exercises for developing monologue speech skills based on the plot text for home reading "Jacob Faithful" by Frederick Marryat.

The study involved 9th grade secondary school students.

Research stages:

1. Preparation of exercises for individual chapters of the plot text "Jacob Faithful" by Frederick Marryat;
2. Developing lesson plans and conducting classes in 9th grade using exercises to test the results of home reading and to develop monologue speech skills;
3. Conducting classes using prepared tasks for the plot text;
4. Systematization and analysis of results.

Research questions

Here are three research questions:

- Is it effective to use materials from plot texts to develop monologue speech skills?
- How to correctly use plot texts for home reading in the process of developing reading and monologue speech skills?
- How should home reading materials (fabular texts) be integrated to develop monologue skills in foreign language lessons?

Tools: Text for home reading "Jacob Faithful" by Frederick Marryat. This study presents a proper approach to using home reading story texts to develop monologue speaking skills in foreign language lessons.

Discussion

Turning to the problem of teaching monologue speech, you should know that its formation occurs in close relationship with other skills of communicative competence. A monologue is a form of speech that is built in by one person, who himself determines the

structure, composition and linguistic means. Monologue speech is characterized by systematicity, therefore it requires internal logic, argumentation, and smooth presentation of thoughts to achieve the goals of communication. A monologue, like other forms of speech, is motivated by a stimulus emanating from a situation. The situation is the starting point for the monologue, then it seems to break away from it, forming its own environment-context [2].

G. K. Zhunussova on the example of developing listening skills, clarified that the correct choice and use of information sources largely determine the effectiveness of the process of teaching a foreign language [3]. The researcher emphasizes that training should be carried out on appropriate materials that cover communicative goals for the development of perceptual and receptive types of speech activity.

A.S. Seidikenov and G.K. Zhantileuova argue that the relevance of using authentic materials in teaching a foreign language lies in their functionality [4, p.65]. By functionality, the researcher understands the orientation of such materials towards real use, since they create the illusion of familiarization with the natural language environment, which is the main factor in successful language acquisition.

Reading authentic texts is a means of obtaining information, developing lexical skills and a way of mastering the rules of logical text construction. An authentic text can support the development of speaking skills. By reading a variety of texts, students begin to understand the specifics of constructing statements of different lengths (a couple of sentences, a full text), different forms (story, argument, monologue/dialogue), i.e. master the logic of constructing statements. According to G.V. Rogova, the role of the text as a template for the development of speaking skills is of great importance for the formulation of statements at the reproductive and productive level, where elements of creativity and independence are mandatory [5, p.76].

G.O. Rakhimbekova points out the following arguments in favor of the use of authentic materials: 1) illustrate the functioning of the language in the form accepted by its speakers and in a natural social context; 2) stimulate the interest of students due to their thematic and stylistic diversity; 3) are the optimal means of teaching the culture of the country of the language being studied; 4) are excellent material for familiarizing yourself with the phraseology of the language being studied [6].

A.T. Iskalieva, A.A. Isalieva, B.Kh. Kurmanov distinguishes the following types of authentic materials:

- 1) Printed materials (newspapers, magazines, posters, maps, books, etc.);
- 2) Video materials (television programs, documentaries and feature films, interviews, amateur videos from social networks).
- 3) Audio materials (musical songs, radio programs, radio advertising, audio books, etc.).
- 4) Multimedia materials [7].

To develop monologue skills, all types of authentic materials can be used in different communicative

situations and with subsequent exercises to consolidate the material.

G.T. Urazumbetova points out that there are two main ways to develop monologue skills [8]. "The path from above": maximum "appropriation" of the content plan of the text, its linguistic material and composition, i.e. everything that can then be applied in the texts that the students themselves will create, building their monologues: introducing students to the text (exercises: read the text, answer questions; plan, order of sentences; brief retelling); conveying the content of the text (on behalf of one of the characters); change of situation. It is on this principle that monologue speech is taught on the basis of authentic texts. In this case, the text serves as a model for constructing a monologue. The "path from below" consists in developing a statement from an elementary unit-sentence to a complete monologue: statements by schoolchildren on a specific topic (statements are constructed in a logical order, students, with the help of the teacher, develop their statements); the stage of forming textual and logical connections between statements; students produce their monologue on a specific topic, including opinions and assessments.

E.A. Zimina and O.S. Khosainova argue about the need to use authentic fable texts as the basis for the development of monologue skills. At the same time, the researchers list the basic requirements for choosing plot texts for students. It has to be noted that E.A. Zimina and O.S. Khosainova consider the retelling of plot texts as one of the exercises for developing monologue speech skills. Therefore, they determined the following requirements for such authentic texts: 1) retelling texts should be feasible for the average student; 2) when selecting texts, it is necessary to be guided by the criteria of compliance with the age interests of students; the subject matter of the texts must correspond to the cognitive, communicative and aesthetic needs of students; 3) the selected materials must meet the goals, objectives and content of teaching a foreign language at the appropriate level according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages [9, p.176]. In addition, plot authentic text containing certain linguocultural information must be understandable to students, since they usually work with such texts on their own (as part of home reading). The linguistic accessibility of the text allows you to focus on its content, structure, and unfamiliar vocabulary. Therefore, it is important that the text offered for reading is based on familiar language material, and that unfamiliar lexical units are either understandable from the context or that they do not interfere with the general understanding of the text.

Home reading is an effective method for developing students' competency skills as part of learning a foreign language. Home reading is an active activity of students working with the texts of fable works and modern journalism, aimed at learning new vocabulary, consolidating knowledge of grammatical forms, expanding students' horizons and regional knowledge. The use of story texts for home reading develops in students such important skills as the ability to work with text, analyze, draw conclusions and generalizations. The development of additional exercises for texts

makes it possible to work on other speech skills based on the text. Reading fable texts performs important functions: developmental, educational and forms information competence in students. Retelling plot texts, writing an essay based on the read text and answering questions about the text are the main types of exercises for developing monologue skills based on the read plot text. However, the teacher can also offer other exercises - writing your own story based on the example of the text you read, creating a presentation based on the text or its characters, etc. Thus, taking into account the variety of possibilities for developing additional exercises for plot texts for the development of monologue skills, we can conclude that their use is an effective method of teaching a foreign language.

Research results

During the educational experiment, based on the technological map of the lesson and the plot text, 6 lessons and 2 writing tests were conducted to construct a full-fledged independent monologue-retelling of the text for each student separately.

Classes with students were structured as follows:

Figure 1. Experiment results

As can be seen from the results presented in Figure 1, the number of student errors in constructing a monologue statement based on the text decreased by an average of 1.5 times for each individual student. This is largely due to the development of the skill of correctly sequencing statements, which influenced its integrity and logic, as well as the coherence of the text. Of great importance was the fact that mandatory check of home reading by performing exercises for it in class encouraged students to actually read the text and write down unknown words and expressions that were worked on in class with the teacher.

Judging by Figure 1, the proposed method of using texts for home reading to develop monologue speech skills is effective, since students learned to better compose a monologue statement after reading each individual chapter. Also, tasks for the plot text helped students remember new vocabulary from the text and colloquial expressions that can be used in speech.

Based on the results of the experiment, in the last lesson a discussion was held with students about the

- 1) checking new vocabulary from the chapter of the story for home reading;
- 2) retelling the chapter read by several students;
- 3) performing exercises for home reading texts to reflect on the material and develop monologue speech skills.

During the experiment and preparation of additional training exercises, emphasis was placed on:

- explanation of new vocabulary from each chapter of the home reading text;
- highlighting the most important information in each chapter of the home reading text;
- teaching the practice of dividing a chapter into main information blocks that students must tell (retell);
- strengthening lexical knowledge and skills to consistently construct a statement (retelling / detailed answer to a question) to compose a monologue expression.

During the initial attempts to retell a chapter of a plot text, many students made mistakes in the factual content and sequence of composing a written monologue.

need to study texts for home reading in class to reinforce the material and develop communication skills. During the discussion, students confirmed the following didactic aspects of using plot texts:

- 1) The text chosen for home reading was interesting, contained a lot of new vocabulary and colloquial expressions, so they were easy to understand from the context and remember;
- 2) Students were able to practice reading skills, monologue speech (oral and written);
- 3) Students were able to learn new vocabulary by reflecting on the chapter in class and while doing exercises for the text;
- 4) Students' horizons, cultural and communicative knowledge have expanded, and their motivation to learn a foreign language has increased.

Conclusion

The development of monologue speech skills is possible not only in class, but also in the process of doing homework. To develop monologue speech skills, it is rational to use plot texts as an example and source of

lexical and grammatical information. Fabulous texts are multifaceted authentic texts that consist of a sequence of events ordered into a logically presented text that ends with a specific ending and conclusion.

The development of monologue skills based on plot texts involves systematic work on students' assimilation of new vocabulary and the practice of constructing coherent statements. Relying on a plot text is an effective way to teach students to logically build the logic of a statement. The use of story texts in foreign language lessons develops such important skills in students as the ability to read and work with text, analyze, evaluate, criticize, draw conclusions and generalizations. In addition, reading authentic fable texts allows students to independently develop creative thinking using a foreign language and the skills of constructing fable stories in accordance with the norms of text structure.

As a result of the study, it was established that the use of plot texts is an effective method for developing monologue speech skills.

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